

Do attachment style and impulsiveness predict dark triad traits?

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An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Previous research has delineated distinct patterns of attachment style and impulsiveness associated with each Dark Triad trait. However, these investigations often occur in isolation, prompting scholars to advocate for the use of multiple correlational models to comprehensively understand the development of Dark Triad traits. Addressing this gap in the literature, the current study aimed to concurrently investigate the predictive roles of attachment style and impulsiveness in each DT trait within the general population. Additionally, we explored whether dimensions of attachment and impulsiveness mediated the identified relationships. Participants ($N = 95$) completed an online anonymous survey comprising three questionnaires: the Revised Adult Attachment Scale, the Barrett Impulsiveness Scale, and the Dark Triad Index (DTI-2). Data were analysed using multiple regression and mediation. Results revealed that attachment style and impulsiveness could predict Dark Triad traits, with each variable making distinct contributions to the manifestation of these traits. Key findings include: (1) Attachment avoidance positively predicted Machiavellianism; (2) Non-planning impulsiveness negatively predicted positive narcissism while positively predicting negative narcissism; and (3) Attentional impulsiveness positively predicted psychopathy, with motor impulsiveness mediating this relationship. The implications of interpersonal styles and intrapersonal behavioural tendencies in predisposing individuals to DT personality traits were discussed. Limitations include the reliance on self-report measures and a cross-sectional design. Future directions may involve validating and refining the DTI-2 measure to allow differentiation between primary and secondary psychopathy

Keywords: attachment styles; dark triad of personality; impulsiveness; Machiavellianism; narcissism; psychopathy

The Dark Triad of personality was introduced by Paulhus and Williams (2002), encompassing a set of three subclinical maladaptive and socially aversive personality traits – psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and Narcissism. Individuals with psychopathy exhibit impulsive, antisocial, and thrill-seeking behaviours, alongside low empathy and anxiety (Hare, 1993). Those with Machiavellianism tend to employ manipulative tactics, display immorality, and harbour a cynical worldview (Christie & Geis, 1970). Narcissistic individuals typically demonstrate grandiosity and self-centeredness, often exhibiting a sense of entitlement, control, and superiority (Raskin & Hall, 1979). Extensive attention has been given to examining psychopathy and narcissism within clinical and forensic populations in the personality disorders literature, with subsequent adaptation to subclinical manifestations (Lilienfeld & Andrews, 1996). In nonclinical community samples, the Dark Triad is studied in a continuum, without differentiating between what is considered ‘normal’ and ‘abnormal’ (Lyons, 2019). Muris and colleagues (2017) in their meta-analysis highlighted all Dark Triad traits, especially psychopathy, are associated with higher levels of adverse psychosocial correlates. These encompass antisocial and criminal outcomes (Pechorro et al., 2022), as well as interpersonal difficulties in the form of aggression (Zhu & Jin, 2021) and emotional dysregulation (Rogier et al., 2020).

While the Dark Triad traits share a core of manipulation, callousness, and selfishness (Jones & Figueredo, 2013), they have distinct structures and are conceptualised distinctively (Rogoza & Cieciuch, 2018). Hare and Neumann (2008) conceptualised psychopathy in a four-factor model capturing its interpersonal (manipulative), affective (callousness), antisocial conduct (poor behavioural control), and lifestyle (erratic) dimensions. Alternative perspectives, such as the two-factor model, categorises psychopathy into primary and secondary types (Hare & Neumann, 2008). Primary psychopathy encompasses traits related to interpersonal and affective aspects, including emotional detachment and callous manipulation, while secondary psychopathy involves risky and antisocial behaviours influenced by emotional disturbances and exhibited through impulsive actions (Levenson et al., 1995).

Machiavellianism embodies a strategic and manipulative approach to achieving one's goals, often involving a calculated consideration of costs and benefits, even if it entails resorting to deceitful or unethical means (Jones & Paulhus, 2009). It reflects a mindset that prioritises personal gain and power, utilising flexibility and cunning to navigate complex social and political landscapes. Rauthmann and Will (2011) proposed understanding Machiavellianism in dimensions of desires, cognition, affect, and behaviour. Machiavellian desires revolve around self-interest characterised by self-promotion and self-protection. This self-serving mindset is complemented by a negative worldview and a sceptical view of others. Emotionally, individuals with Machiavellian tendencies display a low level of remorse and emotional detachment. At its core, Machiavellian behaviour manifests as antisocial tendencies, employing strategic tactics for self-benefit and often involving manipulation and exploitation of others.

Narcissism can be understood through various lenses, including the self, interpersonal dynamics, and self-regulation strategies (Campbell & Miller, 2011). Individuals high in narcissism exhibit an inflated self-perception characterised by entitlement and a desire for dominance over others. They view relationships primarily as avenues for personal gain, often engaging in superficial and exploitative interactions. To uphold their grandiose self-image, narcissists employ tactics such as seeking attention, taking credit for others' achievements, and positioning themselves at the forefront.

Scholars distinguish two dimensions of narcissism: positive (grandiose) and negative (vulnerable) (Miller et al., 2011). Both dimensions correlate with low agreeableness but diverge in other aspects. Grandiose narcissism correlates with high extraversion, reflecting boldness and proactive self-promotion, while vulnerable narcissism correlates with high neuroticism, indicating defensive responses to perceived threats. Despite these differences, both forms entail a sense of entitled self-importance (Krizan & Herlache, 2017). The Perceived Control Theory of Narcissism (PCTN; Hansen-Brown, 2018) offers insights into the behavioural disparities between grandiose and vulnerable narcissists. According to PCTN, grandiose narcissists perceive high levels of control over their outcomes, others' behaviours, and their environment. This perception fosters extroverted, assertive,

and promotion-oriented behaviours. In contrast, vulnerable narcissists perceive diminished control, leading to neurotic, reactive, and prevention-focused tendencies as they prioritise self-protection from negative outcomes.

To understand the underlying traits or tendencies that contribute to Dark Triad traits, Koehn and colleagues (2018) highlighted in their review the importance of understanding both interpersonal and intrapersonal factors associated with the traits. Particularly, there has been a significant amount of interest in Dark Triad in relation to attachment style (Jonason et al., 2014) and impulsiveness (Jones & Paulhus, 2011).

Bowlby's (1998) attachment theory provides an influential framework for understanding how early attachment experiences shape individuals' interpersonal functioning and personality development (Fraleay, 2019). Individuals with high attachment avoidance tend to rely on themselves, perceive others as less dependable, and exhibit reduced expression of affection and intimacy in relationships, while those with high in attachment anxiety have a negative self-view, fear rejection, and seek excessive closeness in relationships (Shaver & Mikulincer, 2007). Shaver and Mikulincer (2002) delineated distinct affect-regulation strategies employed by individuals with anxious and avoidant attachment styles, which significantly influence their interpersonal behaviours and cognitive models of self and others. Anxiously attached individuals, driven by a pervasive fear of abandonment and heightened emotional sensitivity, typically employ hyperactivation strategies characterised by clinging or controlling responses in an attempt to maintain proximity to attachment figures and elicit care and support. In contrast, avoidantly attached individuals utilise deactivation strategies, emotionally distancing themselves from others to preserve their sense of autonomy and avoid perceived vulnerabilities associated with interpersonal dependence. These divergent affect-regulation strategies shape distinct working models of self and others, with anxious individuals tending to devalue themselves while relying heavily on external validation, and avoidantly individuals inflating their positive self-views while maintaining a pervasive mistrust of others, thereby fostering a stance of self-reliance and interpersonal control.

Research has consistently shown correlations between attachment styles and the Dark Triad traits. Attachment avoidance has been positively linked to both psychopathy (Jonason et al., 2014) and Machiavellianism (Brewer et al., 2018). Specifically, attachment avoidance was found to be positively predictive of primary psychopathy (Christian et al., 2017; Kyranides & Neofytou, 2021), while attachment anxiety was negatively predictive of secondary psychopathy (Kyranides et al., 2023). Machiavellianism's positive relationship with attachment avoidance is well-established in the literature (Bloxsom et al., 2021; Ináncsi et al., 2015; Kabadzhova, 2017). The strong link between Machiavellianism and attachment avoidance may stem from shared early experiences with unresponsive caregivers, lacking empathy, and overly punitive (Christie & Geis, 1970; Ináncsi et al., 2015). Such experiences, characterised by low-quality or inconsistent parental care, likely contribute to the traits of both Machiavellianism and attachment avoidance (Jonason et al., 2014; Levy et al., 1998). Regarding narcissism, attachment anxiety was found to be negatively correlated with positive narcissism (Nickisch et al., 2020) while positively correlated with vulnerable narcissism (Fossati et al., 2015; Rohmann et al., 2012).

Impulsiveness refers to actions taken quickly without conscious deliberation, behaviours performed with insufficient consideration, and a predisposition to act with minimal forethought, despite typical levels of intelligence (Moeller et al., 2001). It encompasses multiple dimensions, including attentional impulsivity (difficulty maintaining focus), motor impulsivity (acting without prior thought), and non-planning impulsivity (prioritising immediate over long-term outcomes) (Patton et al., 1995). These dimensions correspond to Bechara's model (Bechara et al., 2000), which differentiates motor impulsivity from cognitive impulsivity, with the latter involving the suppression of irrelevant information in working memory. From a neurobiological perspective, while motor and cognitive impulsivity may correspond to distinct regions within the prefrontal cortex, attentional and motor impulsivity are not entirely separable. Tasks requiring motor response inhibition also engage attentional processes, indicating overlapping cognitive demands (Malloy-Diniz et al., 2007).

Strong correlations have been identified between psychopathy, narcissism, and self-reported impulsivity (Malesza & Kalinowski, 2019; Malesza & Ostaszewski, 2016). Jones and Paulhus (2011) proposed that psychopathy is associated with dysfunctional impulsiveness, characterised by rash and maladaptive behaviours, while narcissism aligns with functional impulsiveness, reflecting a confident and deliberate risk-taking approach. In contrast, Machiavellianism typically shows no significant correlation with impulsivity. Machiavellian individuals are known for their strategic thinking, careful planning, and impulse control, prioritising long-term objectives and adaptive flexibility. This stands in stark opposition to the short-sighted, gratification-driven tendencies seen in psychopathy and narcissism (Jones & Paulhus, 2009).

The impulsivity linked to psychopathy often stems from a need for immediate gratification and difficulties with emotional regulation (Levenson et al., 1995). Studies have revealed that higher levels of non-planning impulsiveness are associated with secondary psychopathy (characterised by antisocial behaviours and behavioural disinhibition), whereas primary psychopathy (marked by callousness and manipulative tendencies) shows lower levels of this impulsiveness (Gray et al., 2019; Weidacker et al., 2017). This suggests that individuals with primary psychopathic traits are capable of effective planning and goal-oriented behaviour. Additionally, they demonstrate quick thinking and rapid response abilities, evidenced by higher levels of attentional and motor impulsiveness (Fox & Hammond, 2017; Poythress & Hall, 2011).

We identified that the existing literature on the relationship between attachment style and each Dark Triad trait has primarily been examined in isolation. Although research on impulsiveness and the Dark Triad traits are more often studied simultaneously, they fail to acknowledge the multifaceted nature of the Dark Triad traits, leading to insufficient assessment and a less cohesive theoretical framework, as highlighted by Miller and colleagues (2019). Using the trait narcissism to illustrate the problem, viewing grandiose and vulnerable narcissism as one construct obscures important differences in how different components of narcissism relate to attachment styles (Watts et al., 2017). Two commonly utilised measures of the Dark Triad, namely the Dirty Dozen (DD; Jonason & Webster, 2010) and the Short Dark Triad (Jones & Paulhus, 2012), only offer overall scores for each trait. Our study attempts to address this shortcoming by using the Dark Triad Index (DTI-2; Lawson et al., in press), a measure that includes positive and negative narcissism subscales and hence is measured as separate constructs in this study. The DTI-2 is developed based on the Dirty Dozen.

Furthermore, our review indicated that the existing literature predominantly relies on correlational analysis, limiting the examination of attachment and impulsiveness in predicting variance within each Dark Triad trait. Scholars have underscored the necessity for more sophisticated multiple correlational models to comprehensively grasp the development of Dark Triad traits (Jonason et al., 2014). Notably, there remains a gap in research, as no study to date has concurrently investigated both attachment and impulsiveness dimensions in predicting the Dark Triad traits.

The current study aims to investigate whether attachment styles and impulsiveness could predict each of the Dark Triad traits. Additionally, this study aims to explore whether attachment style or impulsivity mediates levels of Dark Triad traits.

It was therefore hypothesised that: H1: Avoidant attachment positively predicts Machiavellianism; H2: Attachment anxiety positively predicts negative narcissism; H3: Attentional impulsiveness positively predicts psychopathy.

This study aims to contribute to the personality and individual differences literature by examining the distinct contributions of attachment style and impulsiveness to each Dark Triad trait, thereby illuminating how interpersonal experiences and cognitive behavioural tendencies contribute to the manifestations of each Dark Triad trait.

METHODS

Design

A correlational study was conducted. There were five predictor variables – attachment anxiety, attachment avoidant, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsivity. There were four outcome variables – psychopathy, and Machiavellianism, positive narcissism, negative narcissism.

Participants

Participants were recruited via convenient sampling from various online social media platforms through an online study advertisement containing a link to access the questionnaire. Recruitment occurred between December 2023 and February 2024. Of the 139 responses recorded, 95 were complete. The study's inclusion criteria, targeting adults over 18 without a diagnosed mental health condition, were clearly outlined in the study advertisement and participant information sheet. Participants who did not meet these criteria were instructed not to participate.

A sample of 95 participants was used for analysis, meeting the minimum requirement for adequate power in regression analysis as outlined by Tabachnick and Fidell (2013), with $N \geq 50 + 8M$, where M represents the number of predictors (in this case, five predictors, resulting in a sample size of $90 = 50 + 8 * 5$).

The sample consisted of 36 males and 59 females. Participants range from 18–65 years old ($M = 38.18$, $SD = 16.673$). See Appendix A for more demographics. Three participants did not provide their age.

Materials and measures

Participants completed a demographics questionnaire (Appendix B), followed by three questionnaires.

Revised Adult Attachment Scale (RAAS; Collins, 1996a) Based on the Adult Attachment Scale (AAS; Collins & Read, 1990), the RAAS is a measure of adult attachment in close relationships, which assesses attachment-related avoidance and anxiety. It is comprised of three subscales: closeness (comfortable with intimacy), dependency (comfort with reliance on others), and anxiety (fear of rejection and abandonment) (Collins, 1996b). The 18-item self-report measure uses a 5-point Likert scale from 1 = “not at all characteristic” to 5 = “very characteristic of me”. The overall index of attachment-related avoidance is created by averaging and reverse scoring the closeness and dependence dimension scores. The anxiety dimension score serves as an index of overall attachment-related anxiety. Individuals with high scores on attachment avoidant indicate difficulty in trusting others and forming close emotional bonds while high scores on attachment anxiety suggest heightened fear of rejection and abandonment in relationships (Hazan & Shaver, 1987). During development, the measure demonstrated good internal consistency with Cronbach's alphas of .77, .78, and .85 for its close, depend, and anxiety subscales respectively (Collins, 1996a).

Barrett Impulsiveness Scale (BIS-11; Patton et al., 1995) The BIS-11 is a 30-item self-report questionnaire assessing the construct of impulsivity. All items were rated on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = ‘rarely/ never’ to 4 = ‘almost always/ always’. The measure has three subscales, each measuring a different dimension of impulsivity: attentional impulsiveness defined as difficulty staying focused on the task at hand, motor impulsiveness defined as acting quickly without thinking, and non-planning impulsiveness defined as an orientation towards the present rather than the future (Patton et al., 1995). Higher scores reflect higher levels of impulsiveness. The internal consistency of subscales ranges between .59 and .74 (Stanford et al., 2009).

Dark Triad Index (DTI-2) The DTI-2 is a 60-item self-report questionnaire designed to assess the DT personality traits. Based on the 12-item DD (Jonason & Webster, 2010), the DTI-2 consists of four subscales assessing psychopathy, Machiavellianism, positive narcissism, and negative narcissism. An example statement is 'I often use my social skills to gain advantage'. Participants rate their agreement with each item on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). To mitigate response biases, 4 items were phrased to reflect the absence of Dark Triad traits and were reverse scored accordingly. All four subscales demonstrated good reliability with $\alpha = .792$, $\alpha = .742$, $\alpha = .851$, and $\alpha = .857$ for psychopathy, Machiavellianism, positive narcissism, and negative narcissism respectively (Appendix C).

Procedure

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from Loughborough University's Human Participants Sub-Committee (study reference 2023-14780-16135) and registered on LEON (Project ID: 14780). The study was advertised on Instagram. Upon accessing a provided link to Qualtrics, participants were presented with an anonymous online survey. Before proceeding, participants were required to review a participant information sheet (Appendix D) and then provide informed consent by ticking the 'I voluntarily agree to take part in this study' box (Appendix E). Participants completed a demographics questionnaire, followed by the three questionnaires ordered in the materials and measures section. Upon completion, participants were presented with a debriefing statement (Appendix F). The online survey typically took around 15 minutes to complete.

Data analysis

Four standard multiple regressions were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 29). Preliminary checks ensured compliance with assumptions for standard multiple regression, including linearity, homoscedasticity, normality, and multicollinearity, all of which were met (see Appendix G, Appendix H, Appendix I, and Appendix J). While Tolerance values for attentional and motor impulsiveness were .458 and .499 respectively, multicollinearity was not violated as all Pearson Correlation coefficients remained below .9.

Demographic characteristics were examined, followed by Two-Tailed Pearson's correlation analysis to explore relationships between attachment dimensions, impulsivity constructs, and Dark Triad traits.

Four standard multiple regression analyses were conducted to assess the predictive influence of five variables: attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness, on each of the Dark Triad traits (psychopathy, Machiavellianism, positive narcissism, and negative narcissism). To further investigate the relationships identified in the regression analyses, mediation analysis was performed using Jamovi version 2.5 (The Jamovi Project, 2024). This exploratory mediation analysis aimed to determine whether any of the predictor variables acted as mediators, addressing the limited research available on the mediating roles of these variables.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics for all predictors and outcome variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics: Mean (and Standard deviation) of Subscales from the Revised Adult Attachment Scale, Barrett Impulsiveness Scale, and Dark Triad Index

	Mean	SD
RAAS Attachment Anxiety Subscale	2.77	0.93
RAAS Attachment Avoidant Subscale	2.84	0.64
BIS-11 Attentional Impulsiveness Subscale	16.35	3.05
BIS-11 Motor Impulsiveness Subscale	21.73	3.51
BIS-11 Nonplanning Impulsiveness Subscale	24.59	4.86
DTI-2 Psychopathy Subscale	9.31	2.88
DTI-2 Machiavellianism Subscale	10.58	2.43
DTI-2 Positive Narcissism Subscale	11.94	3.81
DTI-2 Negative Narcissism Subscale	12.12	4.13

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; DTI-2: Dark Triad Index

Correlations

Two-tailed Pearson's correlations (Table 2) revealed all dimensions of impulsiveness were positively correlated with psychopathy (attentional impulsiveness $r = 0.47$, $p < 0.01$, motor impulsiveness $r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$, non-planning impulsiveness $r = 0.33$, $p < 0.01$). Attentional impulsiveness showed the strongest correlation to psychopathy, a medium to large effect size ($r = 0.47$). Attentional and motor impulsiveness were positively correlated with Machiavellianism (attentional impulsiveness $r = 0.34$, $p < 0.01$, motor impulsiveness $r = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$), demonstrating medium effect sizes. Both dimensions of attachment style negatively correlated with positive narcissism (attachment anxiety $r = 0.20$, $p < 0.05$, attachment avoidance $r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$). As both attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance increase, positive narcissism decreases, although the effect sizes were small to medium (attachment anxiety $r = 0.20$, attachment avoidance $r = 0.27$). Attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, and attentional impulsiveness positively correlated with negative narcissism (attachment anxiety $r = 0.69$, $p < 0.01$, attachment avoidance $r = 0.34$, $p < 0.01$, attentional impulsivity $r = 0.36$, $p < 0.01$). The correlation between attachment anxiety and negative narcissism demonstrated a large effect size ($r = 0.69$).

Table 2
 Correlation Matrix of All Predictor Variables: Attachment Style, Impulsiveness, and the Outcome Variables of the Dark Triad Personality Traits

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. RAAS (AAnx)	-	0.43**	0.30**	0.08	-0.08	0.03	0.11	-0.20*	0.69**
2. RAAS (AAvo)	0.43**	-	-0.07	-0.21*	-0.13	-0.10	0.17	-0.27**	0.34**
3. BIS-11 (AI)	0.30**	-0.07	-	0.66**	0.48**	0.47**	0.34**	0.10	0.36**
4. BIS-11 (MI)	0.08	-0.21*	0.66**	-	0.50**	0.45**	0.32**	0.13	0.19
5. BIS-11 (NI)	-0.08	-0.13	0.48**	0.50**	-	0.33**	0.17	-0.13	0.18
6. DTI-2 (P)	0.03	-0.10	0.47**	0.45**	0.33**	-	0.75**	0.38**	0.23*
7. DTI-2 (M)	0.11	0.17	0.34**	0.32**	0.17	0.75**	-	0.35**	0.21*
8. DTI-2 (NPos)	-0.20*	-0.27**	0.10	0.13	-0.13	0.38**	0.35**	-	-0.34**
9. DTI-2 (NNeg)	0.69**	0.34**	0.36**	0.19	0.18	0.23*	0.21*	-0.34**	-

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; AAnx: Attachment Anxiety; AAvo: Attachment Avoidance; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; NI: Non-planning Impulsiveness; DTI-2: Dark Triad Index; P: Psychopathy; M: Machiavellianism; NPos: Positive Narcissism; NNeg: Negative Narcissism

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$

Regression analysis

Four standard multiple regressions were conducted in this study to assess the predictive power of attachment style dimensions and impulsiveness dimensions in explaining variance in each of the four Dark Triad traits.

A standard multiple regression was used to examine the ability of five predictor variables: attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness, to predict psychopathy in the general population. All predictor variables were entered simultaneously (Appendix K). See Table 3 for the full list of regression statistics. 22.2% of the variation in psychopathy could be explained by the variation in attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.222$), $F(5, 89) = 6.363$, $p < 0.001$, indicating a small to medium effect size according to Cohen's guidelines. Attentional impulsiveness was the only significant predictor of the model ($\beta = 0.330$, $p = 0.016$), suggesting greater attentional impulsiveness is associated with an increase in psychopathy.

Table 3

Regression table of the relationship between the predictors attachment style, impulsiveness, and the outcome variable psychopathy

	<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	0.159	–	0.068	0.946
RAAS (AAnx)	–0.263	–0.085	–0.757	0.451
RAAS (AAvo)	0.066	0.015	0.139	0.889
BIS-11 (AI)	0.312	0.330	2.454	0.016
BIS-11 (MI)	0.174	0.211	1.642	0.104
BIS-11 (NI)	0.033	0.056	0.616	0.616

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; AAAnx: Attachment Anxiety; AAvo: Attachment Avoidance; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; NI: Non-planning Impulsiveness

A second standard multiple regression was used to examine the ability of the above five predictors to predict Machiavellianism in the general population. All predictor variables were entered simultaneously (Appendix K). See Table 4 for the full list of regression statistics. 14.4% of the variation in Machiavellianism could be explained by the variation in attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness (Adjusted R²= 0.144), $F(5, 89) = 4.171$, $p = 0.002$, indicating a large effect size according to Cohen’s guidelines. Attachment avoidance was the only significant predictor of the model ($\beta = 0.278$, $p = 0.014$), indicating as attachment avoidance increased, Machiavellianism also increased.

Table 4

Regression table of the relationship between the predictors attachment style, impulsiveness, and the outcome variable Machiavellianism

	<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	2.041	–	0.986	0.327
RAAS (AAAnx)	–0.293	–0.112	–0.956	0.342
RAAS (AAvo)	1.054	0.278	2.518	0.014
BIS-11 (AI)	0.201	0.252	1.789	0.077
BIS-11 (MI)	0.169	0.245	1.811	0.073
BIS-11 (NI)	–0.024	–0.048	–0.412	0.681

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; AAAnx: Attachment Anxiety; AAvo: Attachment Avoidance; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; NI: Non-planning Impulsiveness

A third standard multiple regression was used to examine the ability of the above five predictors to predict positive narcissism in the general population. All predictor variables were entered simultaneously (Appendix K). See Table 5 for the full list of regression statistics. 13.1% of the variation in positive narcissism could be explained by the variation in attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness (Adjusted R²= 0.131), $F(5, 89) = 3.843$, $p = 0.003$, indicating a small effect size according to Cohen’s guidelines. In the model, both attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness made a significant contribution to the model (attachment anxiety $\beta = -0.242$, $p = 0.044$; non-planning impulsiveness $\beta = -0.345$, $p = 0.004$). Results indicate as both attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness increased, positive narcissism decreased. Attentional impulsiveness was approaching significance ($\beta = 0.250$, $p = 0.082$).

Table 5

Regression table of the relationship between the predictors attachment style, impulsiveness, and the outcome variable positive narcissism

	<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	16.345	–	4.985	< 0.001
RAAS (AAnx)	–0.994	–0.242	–2.048	0.044
RAAS (AAvo)	–1.009	–0.169	–1.524	0.131
BIS-11 (AI)	0.312	0.250	1.759	0.082
BIS-11 (MI)	0.127	0.117	0.863	0.391
BIS-11 (NI)	–0.271	–0.345	–2.936	0.004

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; AAAnx: Attachment Anxiety; AAvo: Attachment Avoidance; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; NI: Non-planning Impulsiveness

A fourth standard multiple regression was used to examine the ability of the above five predictors to predict negative narcissism in the general population. All predictor variables were entered simultaneously (Appendix K). See Table 6 for the full list of regression statistics. 51.3% of the variation in negative narcissism could be explained by the variation in attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, attentional impulsiveness, motor impulsiveness, and non-planning impulsiveness (Adjusted R² = 0.513), $F(5, 89) = 20.774$, $p < 0.001$, indicating a large effect size according to Cohen’s guidelines. In the model, both attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness made a significant contribution to the model (attachment anxiety $\beta = 0.637$, $p < 0.001$; non-planning impulsiveness $\beta = 0.206$, $p = 0.021$). Results indicate as both attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness increased, negative narcissism increased.

Table 6

Regression table of the relationship between the predictors attachment style, impulsiveness, and the outcome variable negative narcissism

	<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	–3.862	–	–1.452	0.150
RAAS (AAAnx)	2.833	0.637	7.199	< 0.001
RAAS (AAvo)	0.672	0.104	1.251	0.214
BIS-11 (AI)	0.092	0.068	0.636	0.526
BIS-11 (MI)	0.019	0.016	0.159	0.874
BIS-11 (NI)	0.175	0.206	2.343	0.021

Note: RAAS: Revised Adult Attachment Scale; AAAnx: Attachment Anxiety; AAvo: Attachment Avoidance; BIS-11: Barrett Impulsiveness Scale; AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; NI: Non-planning Impulsiveness

Mediation analysis

Following the preliminary results, an exploratory mediation analysis was carried out to investigate the potential mediating role of attachment style and impulsiveness dimensions on the relationships between predictor variables and outcomes variables identified in the regression analyses.

The results revealed a significant indirect mediation effect of attentional impulsiveness on psychopathy via motor impulsiveness ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.045$, 95% CI [0.004, 0.300]), as presented in Table 7 and Figure 1. In the model, attentional impulsiveness significantly influenced motor impulsiveness ($\beta = 0.659$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI [0.584, 0.932]), and motor impulsiveness, in turn, had a significant positive effect on psychopathy ($\beta = 0.244$, $p < 0.039$, 95% CI [0.010, 0.390]). After controlling for the effect of motor impulsiveness, the direct effect of attentional impulsiveness on psychopathy decreased ($\beta = 0.309$, $p = 0.009$, 95% CI [0.074, 0.510]), compared with the total effect ($\beta = 0.469$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI [0.275, 0.612]). This reduction suggests that motor impulsiveness partially

mediates the relationship between attentional impulsiveness and psychopathy in our community sample, augmenting the level of psychopathy. The confidence intervals for the mediation model did not include zero, indicating statistical significance. (Appendix L)

Figure 1
 Mediation model of the effect of motor impulsiveness in the relationship between attentional impulsiveness and psychopathy

*p < 0.05; **p < 0.01

Table 7
 Mediating Effect of Motor Impulsiveness between Attentional Impulsiveness and Psychopathy

Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		β	z	p
				Lower	Upper			
Indirect	AI \Rightarrow MI \Rightarrow P	0.152	0.076	0.004	0.300	0.161	2.01	0.045
Component	AI \Rightarrow MI	0.758	0.089	0.584	0.932	0.659	8.54	< 0.001
	MI \Rightarrow P	0.200	0.097	0.010	0.390	0.244	2.07	0.039
Direct	AI \Rightarrow P	0.292	0.111	0.074	0.510	0.309	2.62	0.009
Total	AI \Rightarrow P	0.444	0.086	0.275	0.612	0.469	5.15	< 0.001

AI: Attentional Impulsiveness; MI: Motor Impulsiveness; P: Psychopathy

The current study aimed to explore the distinct contributions of attachment style and impulsiveness to DT traits, thereby elucidating the similarities and differences among these traits. Our results confirm all hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3). Key findings include the following. Firstly, attachment avoidance positively predicted Machiavellianism. Secondly, both attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness negatively predicted positive narcissism while positively predicted negative narcissism. Lastly, attentional impulsiveness positively predicted psychopathy. Subsequent mediation analysis demonstrated that motor impulsiveness mediated the relationship between attentional impulsiveness and psychopathy. Overall, our results underscore the importance of considering both attachment style and impulsiveness in comprehensively understanding the manifestation of each Dark Triad trait.

Early attachment experiences, as aforementioned, are believed to influence later personality development (Fraley, 2019), including the Dark Triad (Jonason et al., 2014). The first hypothesis that attachment avoidance will positively predict Machiavellianism was supported, meaning higher levels of attachment avoidance were associated with higher levels of Machiavellian traits in individuals. Our results align with prior research that demonstrated Machiavellianism was positively correlated with attachment avoidance but not attachment anxiety (Bloxsom et al., 2021; Ináncsi et al., 2015; Kabadzhova, 2017).

The robust positive association between attachment avoidance and Machiavellianism can be elucidated through an examination of the affect-regulation strategies and cognitive views of self and others characteristic of avoidantly attached individuals. Shaver and Mikulincer (2002) posit that avoidant individuals utilise deactivation strategies to maintain emotional distance from others, perceiving emotional intimacy as a potential vulnerability. These deactivation strategies, manifesting as emotional detachment, may predispose individuals towards Machiavellian traits by facilitating a detached, distanced approach to interpersonal relationships. Crucially, the cognitive framework underpinning these deactivation strategies involves the suppression of personal deficiencies in favour of self-inflation (Berant et al., 2005), with avoidant individuals viewing themselves more positively than others. This self-aggrandising stance could contribute to the development of Machiavellian traits by fostering self-protection through emotional distance whilst simultaneously promoting self-enhancement via a sense of superiority and entitlement. The perception of others as unreliable or less capable, inherent in this cognitive model, further reinforces a worldview conducive to Machiavellian behaviours. Our conceptualisation extends findings of Ináncsi et al. (2015), suggesting that both attachment avoidance and Machiavellianism are characterised by a negative perception of others, alongside a positive self-view and emotionally detached approach to interactions. This alignment provides a foundation for the cold affect and self-reliance characteristic of Machiavellianism. Moreover, the inflated self-view and diminished view of others not only resembles Machiavellianism's cynical worldview but also facilitates the instrumental use of relationships in Machiavellian behaviour.

Previous scholars have proposed that avoidant attachment and Machiavellianism share etiological origins of low-quality, inconsistent parental care (Jonason et al., 2014; Levy et al., 1998), fostering emotional detachment and a strong need for independence (Bloxsom et al., 2021). Our theoretical framework extends this research by explicating the potential mechanisms through which attachment avoidance may contribute to the development of Machiavellian traits. Consequently, the positive association between attachment avoidance and Machiavellianism can be conceptualised as arising from a shared set of cognitive views and self-protective strategies, rooted in the deactivation strategies characteristic of avoidant attachment.

Consistent with our second hypothesis, we found that attachment anxiety, along with non-planning impulsiveness, positively predicted negative narcissism. This is consistent with previous research findings establishing negative narcissism's positive correlation with attachment anxiety (Fossati et al., 2015; Rohmann et al., 2012; Set, 2020; Smolewska & Dion, 2005) and impulsiveness (Dobrucali & Özkan, 2021; Malesza & Kaczmarek, 2018). Interestingly, the same set of predictors also emerged as significant but negative predictors of positive narcissism. Together, these results suggest a potential protective role of higher levels of attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness against positive narcissism while contributing to negative narcissism.

The PCTN provides a cogent theoretical framework for interpreting these findings, positing that variations in perceived control underpin the distinct behaviours and characteristics associated with positive and negative narcissism (Hansen-Brown, 2018). Individuals with anxious attachment, whose relational experiences are characterised by inconsistent parental proximity and a pervasive fear of rejection, tend to perceive others as unpredictable and life events as beyond their control, mirroring the diminished sense of agency characteristic of vulnerable narcissism (Collins & Read, 1990). This perceived lack of control engenders a sense of helplessness and diminished agency, fostering a reactive approach to interpersonal interactions that aligns with the high neuroticism observed in negative narcissism (Berant et al., 2005; Miller et al., 2011).

The affect regulation strategies employed by anxiously attached individuals offer further insight into the development of negative narcissistic traits, as their persistent self-devaluation and exaggerated emotional displays implicated in hyperactivation strategies while initially developed to elicit care and validation from attachment figures (Shaver & Mikulincer, 2002), may evolve into maladaptive interpersonal tactics characteristic of vulnerable narcissism. Non-planning impulsiveness, which reinforces the immediate gratification sought through these emotional displays, could potentially facilitate rapid, unplanned attempts to secure attention and validation from others. The present-oriented focus and a lack of future consideration implicated in non-planning impulsivity, may serve a dual role as both a coping mechanism and a reinforcing factor for anxiously attached individuals, enabling them to assert immediate control over their environment in response to perceived threats or insecurities.

These impulsive, emotionally-driven behaviours may become habitual over time, creating a self-perpetuating cycle where impulsive emotional reactions strengthen the reliance on manipulative interpersonal strategies. Whilst the immediate gratification derived from successfully eliciting attention or care through impulsive behaviours may temporarily alleviate attachment anxiety (e.g., Relajo-Howell & Stoyanova, 2019) it ultimately reinforces the individual's sense of vulnerability and dependence on others for emotional regulation, fostering negative narcissistic traits within a framework of emotional instability and interpersonal dependency. Conversely, the combination of attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness appears to function as a protective factor against positive narcissism, as the chronic fear of rejection, the need for external validation seeks through dependence, and lack of long-term planning may undermine the self-assuredness and sense of control that positive narcissists strive to maintain, thereby inhibiting the development of grandiose narcissistic traits.

The third hypothesis, regarding the positive prediction of psychopathy by attentional impulsiveness, was confirmed. While all dimensions of impulsiveness positively correlated with psychopathy, only attentional impulsiveness positively predicted psychopathy in the regression analysis. This indicates that higher attentional impulsiveness tendencies were associated with increased levels of psychopathic traits in the sample. Both psychopathy and dysfunctional impulsiveness have been consistently linked to low conscientiousness (Eysenck, 1990; Jones & Paulhus, 2011; Paulhus & Williams, 2002), marked by poor impulse control (Roberts et al., 2014), recklessness (Brunas-Wagstaff et al., 1995), and lack of deliberation and self-discipline (Settles et al., 2012). Attentional impulsiveness, characterised by shifted attention, could contribute to the erratic and disorganised tendencies often observed in individuals with low conscientiousness, resembling those seen in psychopathy.

Subsequent mediation analysis showed significant direct and indirect effects of attentional impulsiveness on psychopathy via motor impulsiveness, suggesting that attentional impulsiveness may contribute to heightened psychopathic traits, partially through its impact on motor impulsiveness. As tasks demanding motor response inhibition also engage cognitive processes (Malloy-Diniz et al., 2007), deficits in attentional control, as indicated by attentional impulsiveness, may lead to impulse motor responses, as reflected in motor impulsiveness. Our results aligned with the observed pattern of impulsiveness associated with primary psychopathy (Fox & Hammond, 2017), indicating a capacity for quick thinking and action, facilitating adaptability to shifting circumstances and the exploitation of manipulation opportunities.

Moreover, their unimpaired planning enables strategic anticipation of others' actions and reactions. Together, these impulsive tendencies facilitate rapid thinking and plan execution, fostering the manipulative behaviours characteristic of primary psychopathy. Furthermore, our use of a new measure developed based on the DD (Jonason & Webster, 2010), which is considered better aligned with primary psychopathy (Katz et al., 2022), provides additional support for these findings.

Our study posed several methodological limitations. Firstly, the utilisation of a cross-sectional design precludes the inference of causality. The observed relationships between attachment style, impulsiveness, and Dark Triad traits could be bidirectional or influenced by unmeasured third variables. For example, early life experiences or genetic factors could contribute to the development

of both insecure attachment and Dark Triad traits, confounding the observed associations. Whilst our cross-sectional study provides valuable insights into the associations between these variables, longitudinal design is necessary to determine the temporal sequence and causal links between them.

Additionally, our study relied exclusively on self-report questionnaires to assess all measured variables, potentially inducing social desirability bias, especially when assessing socially aversive personality traits like the Dark Triad (Edwards, 1957). Given the socially undesirable nature of Dark Triad traits, participants may distort their Dark Triad Scores (Walker & MacCann, 2024), potentially underreporting negative traits such as manipulation and callousness whilst over-reporting desirable traits like empathy and agreeableness. This could lead to an underestimation of Dark Triad traits in our sample and potentially attenuate the observed associations between the predictor variables (attachment style, impulsiveness) and Dark Triad traits. Although we took steps to mitigate social desirability bias, such as ensuring anonymity and using reverse scoring (Nederhof, 1985), these measures may not fully eliminate the bias. Moreover, our study relied on an online convenience sample, which may not be representative of the general population. The self-selection bias inherent in online studies could limit the generalisability of our findings to more diverse populations.

Furthermore, the DTI-2, whilst innovative, requires further validation and cannot differentiate between primary and secondary psychopathy. Researchers have stressed the multifaceted nature of psychopathy (Hare & Neumann, 2008; Jonason et al., 2014), with attachment style and impulsiveness showing distinct patterns across these subtypes. Specifically, primary psychopathic traits correlate with attachment avoidance and lower non-planning impulsiveness, whilst secondary psychopathic traits are associated with attachment anxiety and higher non-planning impulsiveness (Gray et al., 2019; Kyranides & Neofytou, 2021). Consequently, using total scores in our study may obscure significant variations among individual components within psychopathy, thus limiting the depth of our findings. Although the DTI-2 is a promising new measure of Dark Triad traits, its inability to distinguish between primary and secondary psychopathy may have obscured important differences in how attachment style and impulsiveness relate to these subtypes.

Despite these study limitations, it offers several noteworthy implications. Our study sheds light on the complex interplay between interpersonal styles and intrapersonal behavioural tendencies in predisposing individuals to Dark Triad personality traits. Specifically, we found that individuals with insecure attachment styles may exhibit higher levels of Machiavellianism, while those demonstrating impulsive tendencies may be more susceptible to psychopathy. Furthermore, the combination of insecure attachment styles and impulsivity may contribute to negative narcissism, while acting as a protective factor against positive narcissism.

Our study was the first to examine the manifestation of Dark Triad traits with both impulsiveness and attachment style. We observed that attachment style and impulsiveness collectively predicted both positive and negative narcissism, with a large effect size observed for the relationship with negative narcissism, underscoring the importance of studying these constructs together. Additionally, we employed a novel measure (DTI-2) to distinguish between positive and negative narcissism, revealing distinct influences of attachment anxiety and non-planning impulsiveness on each. This highlights the necessity of treating them as distinct constructs, as advocated by scholars (Miller et al., 2019; Watts et al., 2017). Moreover, our study filled a gap in DT literature, which predominantly relies on correlational analysis, by employing more advanced methodologies like regression and mediation. Specifically, we found that while all impulsiveness facets correlate with psychopathy, only attentional impulsiveness emerged as a significant predictor, with motor impulsiveness mediating the relationship. This not only contributes to the literature by elucidating the directionality of the psychopathy-impulsiveness relationship but also offers deeper insights into how specific impulsiveness facets interact to manifest psychopathic traits.

Moving forward, future research could employ longitudinal designs to examine the temporal sequence and potential causal links between attachment style, impulsiveness, and Dark Triad traits. Assessing these variables at multiple time points, starting from childhood, could provide stronger evidence for the developmental trajectories and causal relationships among these constructs. Additionally, future studies could investigate the role of other relevant factors, such as early life

experiences, parenting styles, or genetic influences, in the development of Dark Triad traits. Incorporating these variables could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how attachment style and impulsiveness interact with other risk and protective factors to shape these personality traits. To overcome the limitations of self-report measures, future research could employ a multi-method approach, combining self-reports with informant ratings, behavioural observations, or implicit measures of Dark Triad traits. This would provide converging evidence for the relationships between attachment style, impulsiveness, and Dark Triad traits and reduce the potential impact of social desirability bias.

Furthermore, future research should focus on validating and refining the DTI-2 measure, particularly in its ability to differentiate between primary and secondary psychopathy. By improving the assessment of these subtypes, future studies could provide a more nuanced understanding of how attachment style and impulsiveness relate to specific facets of psychopathy. Finally, more research is needed to replicate and further establish the predictive role of attachment style and impulsiveness on Dark Triad traits, particularly positive and negative narcissism. Future studies could continue to employ more advanced methodologies and complex correlational models, such as structural equation modelling, to understand potential mediators and underlying mechanisms involved in the manifestation of Dark Triad traits. These approaches could help elucidate the complex interplay between interpersonal experiences (e.g., attachment), intrapersonal characteristics (e.g., impulsiveness), and the development of maladaptive personality traits.

In summary, the current study demonstrates that both attachment style and impulsiveness could predict Dark Triad traits within an online community sample, with each making distinct contributions to the manifestation of these traits. This enhances our understanding of the variations in interpersonal experiences and cognitive behavioural tendencies contributing to each Dark Triad trait. We also explored potential mediating mechanisms, elucidating how specific impulsiveness facets interacted to manifest psychopathic traits. Replication studies are warranted to confirm the predictive role of attachment style and impulsiveness, particularly concerning positive and negative narcissism. More sophisticated models are needed to explore mediator variables to further clarify the underlying mechanisms contributing to the development of Dark Triad traits.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Loughborough University

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